

Recognition of Phonemes in A-cappella Recordings using Temporal Patterns and Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a new method for recognizing phonemes in singing is proposed. Recognizing phonemes in singing is a task that has not yet matured to a standardized method, in comparison to regular speech recognition. The standard methods for regular speech recognition have already been evaluated on vocal records, but their performances are lower compared to regular speech.

In this paper, two alternative classification methods dealing with this issue are proposed. One uses Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficient features, while another uses Temporal Patterns. They are combined to create a new type of classifier which produces a better performance than the two separate classifiers. The classifications are done with US English songs. The preliminary result is a phoneme recall rate of 48.01% in average of all audio frames within a song.

1. INTRODUCTION

In music information retrieval (MIR), the lyrics are of value when organizing unlabelled music in a database. The user might have a cover version of a song where the melody or chord progression has been altered, making it difficult to identify the song by these features. It is however likely that the lyrics are fully or partially maintained and the song can instead be identified as a cover version by this information. It is also possible that a user wants to browse songs by their lyrical content using keyword spotting instead of searching by the artist or track name. Finally, studies on mood estimation based on lyrics, such as in Hu et al. [1], could benefit from keyword spotting in lyrics.

For these applications to be robust, it is necessary to be able to classify phonemes with a high accuracy. Phonemes are the smallest units of speech which can be uniquely deciphered, and words can be recognized as a series of phonemes.

This paper is organized as follows: In section 2, the traditional approach to speech recognition is explained and the approaches attempted on speech recognition in singing are surveyed. In section 3, we introduce our proposed method. We present our preliminary results in section 4 and finally conclude the work in section 5.

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Figure 1. Overview of a traditional speech recognition system.

2. RELATED WORK

2.1 Traditional speech recognition

In general, speech recognition is the task of recognizing a sequence of acoustic features, which represents the speech information [2]. Representing the speech by the full frequency spectrum is not feasible as it contains too much information for a pattern classifier to learn. In the traditional approach, small time frames of frequency content are thus often parametrized as Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCC) [3]. A time sequence of MFCC vectors describes the speech units (i.e. words or phonemes). The challenge is to recognize these sequences independent from the natural time variations occurring during speech. Hidden Markov Models (HMM) [4] are often used for this task.

An HMM is a statistical model used to estimate hidden state sequences. Each state represents a specific speech unit (for instance, a phoneme) which generates some acoustic features over time. Given a sequence of acoustic feature observations, the HMM estimates what hidden state sequence did most likely generate these observations. In short, given a sequence of observations as the outcome of a classifier, the HMM can be used to estimate what speech units were most likely being uttered. The most probable acoustic features observed from a specific speech unit is learned from the training data. The classifier and the HMM are called the “acoustic model”. This is often followed by another HMM with statistics about what speech units or words are more likely to follow another in a given language, the “language model”.

The overview of a basic speech recognition system can be seen in Figure 1.

2.2 Speech recognition in singing

In both the works of Mesaros et al. [5] and Fujihara et al. [6] the traditional method is adapted to singing by training a speech recognizer on regular speech and then adapting the acoustic model to singing. This is achieved by trans-

forming the means of a Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) to a small amount of singing data by Maximum Linear Likelihood Regression (MLLR). The reason to do this is the large amount of training data required for the statistics of the GMM to be precise, and there is no such large corpus of annotated singing readily available to our knowledge. The accuracies of these systems are in the range of 33%, but in [6], the model was also trained on 79 songs, yielding an accuracy of 50%. This indicates that it might be better to train on song directly.

An approach to mitigate the need for a large training corpus is to use a different classifier than the GMM. An GMM need much more data to estimate the free parameters (means and covariances) [2, 7] than for instance a Multi Layer Perceptron (MLP). An MLP or a similar classifier could be connected with an HMM as an alternative approach to the traditional GMM-HMM implementations, as done in Boulard [8]. We call this an MLP-HMM hybrid. The performance of this system naturally depends on the performance of the classifier itself. In the work of Szepanek et al. [9], several classifiers are evaluated on sung phonemes extracted from song which were isolated from background music. The best classifier is the Support Vector Machine (SVM) with an accuracy of 55%. This is however done on isolated MFCC frames for each phoneme and not continuous modelling. Thus, the performance will most likely decrease when the transitions of the phonemes are classified as well. To our knowledge, the MLP-HMM hybrid implementation has not been tried on singing.

In addition to the previously mentioned methods, a number of alternative approaches has been proposed. In the work of Dittmar et al. [10], a Dynamic Time Warping (DTW) approach is attempted for keyword spotting. The user provides a singing query and the MFCCs of this query are matched against several target songs, with the allowance of some time variation due to the DTW. The disadvantage is the demand for an acoustic query, though this could be generated by speech synthesis of a text query. The advantage is that there is no need for training data, making this method instantly usable.

The last surveyed method is the work of Feng et al. [11], where the self-similarity sequences of several popular songs are generated. The self-similarity sequences are then learned by a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN). An acoustic input query is matched to the database by the RNN, which is trained to recognize a time sequence similar to the self-similarity sequence. The results are useful, but again constrained by the need of an acoustic query, which also needs to be sung with the correct melody.

2.3 Temporal pattern (TRAP) classification

A different method that attempts to overcome the problem of phonemes being influenced by its context and the need for a large training corpus is the Temporal Pattern (TRAP) algorithm as done by Hermansky et al. [12] and Boulard et al. [13]. In this method, the phonemes are classified in a much longer time context than usual. This is based on the assumption that a phoneme is influenced by the previous and next phonemes in such a long context. In order to

do this, several sub bands are extracted from the full frequency spectrum and the log energies of each band are calculated. Each phoneme can then be classified by the energy trajectory of each frequency band. Time-frames of the trajectories are cut out. These are normalized and windowed, for instance with a Hanning window, and fed to an MLP. The MLP produces a phoneme estimation per trajectory. The estimations from all trajectories are fed to a merger MLP which calculates the final phoneme estimation of the center of the window. This method was proven to perform very well and even outperform traditional systems under noisy circumstances. The reason for this is found in the usage of sub-bands, as noise is often frequency selective and thus will not affect all bands.

2.4 Challenges

To summarize, the biggest problem when recognizing lyrics seems to be the lack of a proper training corpus. Training the acoustic models using one of the standardized speech corpora like TIMIT¹ and then adapting them to singing is one solution [5]. However, training the acoustic models directly on song may improve the performance [6]. Another way to further reduce the amount of required training data is to move from GMM classifiers to MLPs, thus reducing the amount of free parameters to be estimated. In [2] it is measured empirically, that for an MLP to reach the same performance of an GMM, only 1/20 of the free parameters are needed. In [8], experiments shows that “parameter to training-sample ratio” can be as high as 10, and still give good generalization on a MFCC-based phoneme recognition. This is obtained by early stopping, using an validation set.

3. PROPOSED METHOD

In this project, we propose a novel phoneme classifier by both classifying single-frames with an MLP using MFCC features and an MLP using long context TRAP features. The motivation behind this is that the single MFCC frame is expected to give a better representation of the formants of the singing, giving a high classification rate of the vowels and nasals. In addition, MFCCs are pitch robust to a certain degree, which is important in singing. On the other hand, this single frame-based classification does not deal well with the temporally changing nature of fricatives and stops like /G/ or /P/. This is where the TRAP classifier is expected to have an advantage given the temporal context. By combining the advantages of these two classifiers, we assume that the performance will increase compared to the separate classifiers. The TRAP method has not yet been tried on singing, but are expected to perform well. A system overview can be seen in Figure 2.

3.1 MFCC/MLP classifier

The MFCC feature extraction is implemented as described in [14]. The MFCCs are extracted from 25 ms audio frames with a 10 ms hop size. The first 13 coefficients (including

¹ www.ldc.upenn.edu/Catalog/LDC93S1.html[last visited: 30-3-2012]

Figure 2. A overview of the proposed system. A MFCC and a TRAP based classifier are doing parallel classification and then combined to compliment each other.

C_0) are used. The MFCCs of each song are standardized independently and the Δ and $\Delta\Delta$ coefficients are calculated over five frames giving the direction and acceleration of the MFCC vectors as described in [2]. This gives the features a 105 ms time context (from both Δ and $\Delta\Delta$), which is still much shorter than for the TRAP features. These features are concatenated to 39 features which are often referred to as the MFCC39 features [2].

The MFCC39 features are extended with the spectral flatness and the spectral centroid (both from [15]), two simple features that describe the wideness of the spectral energy and the low/high frequency ratio respectively. Finally, the extended feature vector is decorrelated using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) over all songs. This should make it easier for the classifier to learn the patterns.

The feature vector is fed to an MLP with one hidden layer of 40 neurons and the output layer uses the “Softmax” transfer function [16], which makes it possible to use the outputs directly as probabilities.

3.2 TRAP/MLP classifier

An overview of the classifier using the TRAP features can be seen in Figure 3. First the sub-band log energies are calculated by applying a filter-bank of triangular filters to the spectrogram. The band frequencies used for this system can be seen in Table 1 and calculated by merging 40 Mel-based bands in groups of five. The spectrogram is calculated in frames of 25 ms with a 10 ms hop size.

A time-frame is cut from each energy trajectory and windowed with a Hanning window, giving the TRAP feature. A TRAP feature spans 91 frames of 10 ms. A Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT) is used for dimension reduction. This is also believed to make the system more tolerant to time variance. The reason for this is that the frequency content of the energy trajectories remains the same when the window slides over a specific phoneme. The energy trajectories for each band are concatenated to a single feature vector and fed to an MLP, with 30 hidden neurons and a “Softmax” output transfer function. In the original implementations, an MLP classifies each individual band and a merger MLP does the final classification from each band output. It is found that having a single MLP classifying all bands at once works better, as also suggested in [2].

Figure 3. Overview of the classifier using TRAP features. A time-window is sliding over the frequency spectrum classifying the center frame one at a time.

Band number	Frequency range
1	133 Hz - 533 Hz
2	467 Hz - 866 Hz
3	800 Hz - 1228 Hz
4	1147 Hz - 1732 Hz
5	1617 Hz - 2443 Hz
6	2281 Hz - 3446 Hz
7	3217 Hz - 4860 Hz
8	4537 Hz - 6856 Hz

Table 1. The frequency sub-bands of the TRAP system. The band extraction is done using a triangular filter bank.

3.3 Combining two classifiers

The outputs of the two classifiers are combined to complement each other. We attempted to use an MLP to combine the outputs in a way so phoneme confusion of the two classifiers was learned and taken into account. For instance, if one classifier often confuses /N/ with /M/, while the other classifies the /N/ with high accuracy, the MLP could maybe learn to compensate for this.

3.4 Viterbi decoding

The training set is used for building a matrix of transition probabilities between phonemes, simply by frequency counting each transition per frame. The Viterbi decoder is used to find the most likely phoneme sequence using the classifier outputs and statistics about phoneme transition probabilities, for instance the probability of going from /EH/ to /L/. This should improve performance by reducing improbable phoneme transitions and make transitions with high probability more likely.

3.5 Dataset

The initial dataset for this project consists of 12 fully phoneme labelled a-cappella versions of mainstream tracks with different singers. The tracks are of studio quality, but not “dry” tracks. Different post-processing methods like reverb and EQ has been applied, which most likely decreased the overall performance [17].

The phoneme set used is the one used by CMU Sphinx².

²<http://cmusphinx.sourceforge.net/> [last visited: 30-3-2012]

1: /AA/	2: /B/	3: /CH/
4: /D/	5: /DH/	6: /EH/
7: /ER/	8: /EY/	9: /F/
10: /G/	11: /HH/	12: /IH/
13: /IY/	14: /JH/	15: /K/
16: /L/	17: /M/	18: /N/
19: /OW/	20: /P/	21: /R/
22: /S/	23: /T/	24: /UH/
25: /V/	26: /Y/	27: /SIL/
28: INHALE		

Table 2. The reduced phoneme set. The numbers refer to the numbers in the confusion matrix in Figure 5

The CMU phonetic dictionary³ is used for looking up the phonetic spelling. The transcriptions are not done by a professional, so the dictionary lookup is used as the true pronunciation, without considering variations. The CMU phoneme set contains 39 phonemes.

Having only 12 transcribed songs, the training data does not represent each phoneme equally and some phonemes are not represented at all. The framework is designed so that it is possible to merge an under-represented phoneme with a similar sounding phoneme. To even out the distribution, we need to exclude some data of the over-represented phonemes. If we do not do this, the classifier would tend to only learn the over-represented phonemes. Unison or harmony voices are present in some of the training songs. These regions are masked out to only get clear solo a-cappella training data. Our final set of phonemes can be seen in Table 2. We end up with 26 phoneme classes and two classes for silence and inhaling.

Around 16.000 audio frames are available for training, 8.000 for validation and 6.000 for testing for each cross-validation fold. The annotations can be found on http://www.idmt.fraunhofer.de/en/Departments_and_Groups/smt/phoneme_annotations.html

3.6 Labelling

The first songs were manually labelled one phoneme at a time. The free software Audacity⁴ was used. After four songs were labelled, the classifiers were trained with this training data to assist in the labelling of more songs. This is called the seed model [18] and made the annotation process much faster. The boundaries of sentences were manually aligned. Each word within a sentence was then coarsely time-aligned automatically using the seed model. This alignment was refined manually, after which the same procedure was applied to align phonemes within the word boundaries. All frames within a phoneme boundary were assigned to that phoneme class. The labelling process from sentence to phoneme level is illustrated in Figure 4.

³<http://www.speech.cs.cmu.edu/cgi-bin/cmudict>[last visited: 30-3-2012]

⁴<http://audacity.sourceforge.net/>[Last visited: 30-3-2012]

Figure 4. At the bottom, the sentence level annotations are shown, next then word level and finally the phoneme level in the top. The upper row is the spectrogram for visual aid of the labelling.

4. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

4.1 Evaluation method

Due to the time consuming process of annotating the songs, only 12 fully annotated songs are available at this time of the project. These are used for both training and performance evaluation. A leave-one-out cross validation (CV) is used for evaluating performance by training the acoustic model on 11 songs and measuring recall rate on the 12th. This training procedure is done 12 times, each time leaving one song out. Finally the mean of the 12 performance measures gives an overall indication of the performance. The standard deviation of the performance measures gives an indication whether the results are consistent or not. For the training procedure, early stopping is used based on a validation set.

Each 10 ms audio frame is classified to either one of the phoneme classes or the silence or inhale class. The performance measures are presented as recall rates of phonemes.

4.2 Performance

The performance measure for each classifier on the individual phonemes can be seen in Table 3. It is observed that stops like /K/ and /P/ are indeed better recognized by the TRAP method, while most vowels and nasals are best classified by the MFCC features. In addition, phonemes with high frequency content, like /S/ and /INHALE/ are also better classified by the TRAP method, because of the high frequency bands. Finally, the combination of the two classifiers gives an overall better performance compared to the two individual sub-classifiers for 19 out of 28 phonemes.

Some stops like /G/ and /D/ gets a higher classification rate with the MFCC features. The reason for this is not certain, but can be because that the Δ and $\Delta\Delta$ coefficients are sufficient to model the articulation motions or the TRAP method confuses this with another stop.

The per-phoneme standard deviation gets quite high over the cross-validation, in the range of 15%, meaning that the results are not reliable with this amount of data, but

still gives a trend of the advantage of using TRAP and MFCC features together. The overall recall rates of all time-frames in a song can be seen in Table 4. With the combined classifier we get a recall rate of 48.01%. On two songs, the recall rate gets as high as 55%.

It was found, that simply merging the output of the two MLPs by simple averaging each output, gave a better result than the proposed classifier merging method using an third MLP. For the TRAP decorrelation, it was found that keeping 24 DCT coefficients for each energy trajectory gave a good result. For the MFCC features it was found, that omitting the PCA decorrelation yielded better results.

The preliminary results are not directly comparable to every surveyed papers, as some are on a higher classification level using word and language models. In addition, the source material is different, as some approaches use non a-cappella tracks and performs their own vocal isolation.

The most similar results are from [19], where an MLP reaches a recall rate of 41% in average using MFCCs. This is with a set of only 15 carefully isolated phonemes, but with artifacts from an vocal isolation algorithm. Seen in that context, we obtain a recall rate of 48.01% in average of a full track, which is a harder task because the phoneme transitions also need to be classified. If we look on our classifier using only MFCCs however, we still get 44.87% recall rate. So it is clear that the combined TRAP and MFCC method is an improvement of the separate classifiers.

4.3 Confusion matrix

In Figure 5 the confusion matrix is depicted. The confusion matrix is constructed from the cross validation. The obvious confusions are between for instance the /EH/ and /IH/ vowels, the /N/ and /M/ nasals and finally /S/ and /T/, which both have a high frequency hiss. But there is also some confusions between more unrelated phonemes. These confusions are harder to explain. Some confusions might be a consequence of alternative pronunciation in the song compared to the dictionary lookup. But most likely the models needs much more training data to reach a better performance. In addition, as the consonants are short, it is easy for the Viterbi decoder to accidentally skip them. A better statistical description of the transition matrix would perhaps improve this.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

A novel classifier is presented, and while the dataset is too small to be able to generalize well, the initial research indicates that classifying on MCFE features and TRAP features each have its advantage modelling the harmonic content and the temporal trajectories respectively. Most vowels and nasals gets a better classification rate with the MFCC features, while some fricatives and stops are better classified by the TRAP features. The average recall rate of all audio frames in a song is currently 48.01%, so there is still a lot of room for improvements. To improve performance, possible approaches are applying another HMM with language statistics, which often improves performance. The

Phoneme	MFCC	TRAP		Combined
/AA/	40.46%	35.35%	*	41.88%
/B/	29.18%	29.13%	*	31.13%
/CH/	7.89%	23.15%		9.99%
/D/	17.74%	10.92%		13.89%
/DH/	16.79%	4.91%		12.40%
/EH/	41.13%	41.69%	*	48.73%
/ER/	24.02%	26.51%	*	26.75%
/EY/	32.97%	30.04%	*	36.75%
/F/	40.54%	32.22%	*	45.23%
/G/	31.62%	22.93%		27.45%
/HH/	22.40%	22.32%	*	25.91%
/IH/	21.96%	19.25%	*	23.73%
/IY/	38.74%	31.72%	*	40.25%
/JH/	1.25%	5.11%	*	5.80%
/K/	11.82%	16.22%		15.57%
/L/	13.46%	4.11%		9.79%
/M/	31.41%	27.33%	*	31.99%
/N/	27.29%	22.41%		26.21%
/OW/	47.07%	36.00%	*	49.56%
/P/	0.59%	2.31%	*	2.31%
/R/	18.74%	13.59%		14.90%
/S/	67.65%	69.97%	*	76.40%
/T/	19.90%	9.38%		14.14%
/UH/	33.83%	25.89%	*	34.08%
/V/	25.70%	21.37%	*	26.71%
/Y/	33.48%	28.10%	*	38.21%
/SIL/	63.74%	73.37%	*	73.94%
/BREATH/	49.61%	62.84%	*	64.06%

Table 3. The recall rate for each individual phoneme, both for the individual classifiers and the combined classifier. The sub-classifier with the best performance is written in bold case. An asterisk marks where the combined classifier is better than the separate.

Classifier	Avg. recall
MFCC	44.8%
TRAP	42.16%
Combined	48.01%

Table 4. The overall performance of the system as measured as average recall rate.

need for a larger training set is most urgent, though. In Shin et al. [20], it is concluded that SVMs are better suited for small training sets. It could be interesting to investigate whether this could also be the case for this study. Also, as shown in [5], the acoustic models are gender influenced. With more data, separate models could be trained for male and female, most likely giving better results.

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Figure 5. The confusion matrix from the test data. The numbers represents the phoneme classes from Table 2. The entries on the diagonal corresponds to correct classifications. Dark represents a high classification rate.

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